

STRUCTURE OF THE UNIVERSE

(by Albert Hoffmann 2019)

[01] On 15 March 1840, 6 o'clock in the morning, a humble school teacher but talented musician heard a clear voice in his heart saying: "*Rise, take your pen and write!*" At that stage Jakob Lorber was already 40 years old and was on the verge of departure to take up a long awaited position of assistant musical director at the theatre in Trieste. But when hearing the mysterious inner voice he immediately declined this lucrative offer which would have provided him with a necessary financial stability in his life and instead gave his fullest attention to write down what the inner voice dictated to him. To support himself he made his scant living by giving music lessons and tuning instruments. At times he had to be supported by his friends to survive.

[02] Jakob Lorber was born on 22 July 1800 in Kanischa, a small village in the Jahring parish, the Duchy of Styria in south-eastern Austria to a peasant family, Michael Lorber and his wife Maria, née Tautscher. He was trained as a village teacher.

[03] A brief biography by his friend Karl Gottfried Ritter von Leitner indicates that Lorber was an uncomplicated person. He was the kind of person when having ten pennies in his pocket he would give six to a person who was even poorer than he and kept four for himself. He was raised Catholic and was never married. When Lorber's father died, Lorber inherited 12,000 gulden which he loaned to his brother, a loan which was never repaid.

[04] Lorber was observed during his daily writing sessions by well-educated men in the city of Graz, such as the mayor of Graz, Anton Hüttenbrenner, his brother the composer Anselm Hüttenbrenner, the poet and Secretary to the Estates Karl Gottfried von Leitner, Dr. Anton Kammerhuber, Dr. Carl-Friedrich Zimpel, pharmacist of Graz Leopold Cantily and others. At times his friends would do the writing of what Lorber dictated to them.

[05] Lorber inherited his musical talent from his father who also taught him to play the violin and piano. At one stage Lorber was taking lessons from the virtuoso violinist Paganini, and once gave a violin concert at the La Scala Opera House in Milan.

Fig. 1: Jakob Lorber.

[06] Except for a few interruptions Lorber wrote daily for the next 24 years until his death in 1864 what this mysterious inner voice dictated to him. In total he brought to paper 10,000 pages in print, generally referred to as the New Revelation (NR). The handwritten manuscripts are preserved in the archives of the Lorber Publisher in Bietigheim, Germany. During his writing sessions he would be sitting completely relaxed at his table and kept writing continuously without interruptions or rereading at any stage what he has written. He could stop writing in the middle of a sentence and resume writing the next day without rereading the material of his previous session. Only when completing a session he would read what he has written and fully comprehend the content of it through tears and emotional exclamations. At times Lorber also received inner visions about the written content.

[07] Lorber's writings reveal that the inner voice spoke freely in first person as the voice of Jesus Christ. Everything Lorber wrote was dictated to him through the inner voice. He did not write any books out of himself. Lorber never received any compensation for his writings because the books were only published after his death in 1864.

[08] Quite often the question is raised why was it necessary to give to mankind a new revelation in addition to the Bible. Doesn't the Bible explain Christianity sufficiently? The first and most obvious answer to this question is that the Lord Himself promised us a future extension on the Bible. Several scripture texts given by the Apostle John are pointing to an expansion of his Gospel in future times. With the New Revelation Jesus in fact did good on His promise when He said: "*These things have I spoken unto you in proverbs: but*

the time cometh, when I shall no more speak unto you in proverbs, but I shall shew you plainly of the Father." (King James Version [KJV] John 16:25. Another indication of future additions to the Bible are: "*And many other signs truly did Jesus in the presence of his disciples, which are not written in this book;*" (KJV John 20:30) and "*And there are also many other things which Jesus did, the which, if they should be written every one, I suppose that even the world itself could not contain the books that should be written. Amen.*" (KJV John 21:25) And in John 16, 12 we read: "*I have much more to say to you, more than you can now bear. 13 But when he, the Spirit of truth, comes, he will guide you into all the truth. He will not speak on his own; he will speak only what he hears, and he will tell you what is yet to come.*"

[09] Secondly, when considering the historical development of Christianity over the past two-thousand years, especially with regard to the most despicable atrocities committed in the name of Christianity, it is clear that mankind did not at all understand the principals of the Christian message of love as brought to us by Christ. Perhaps the most misunderstood concept of Christianity by all past and present church leaders is that the Kingdom of God can only be found inside of man and not outwardly. All unspeakable human suffering caused in the so called name of Christianity was the result of trying to enforce an outwardly or worldly religion on to people making ceremonies, relics, holy places, religious icons, saints, buildings, doctrines, etc. the focus of religious belief. But that Jesus once had said to the Pharisees "*The kingdom of God does not come with your careful observation, nor will people say, 'Here it is,' or 'There it is,' because the kingdom of God is within you.*" (Luke 17:20-21), is completely ignored. Incidentally, a better translation for "*careful observation*" is pageantry, pomp, ostentation, outer splendour or science.

[10] The twisting of faith culminated when religion during the middle ages was replaced by dark superstition and fear. When people saw a comet flying through the sky or an eclipse of the sun or moon took place, they believed it was a sign of bad luck coming. This kind of enforced, deeply engrained superstitious and corrupted belief threatened to smother any further sensible spiritual development of mankind. To free man's disposition from such superstitious shackles but at the same time not interfering with man's free will by God, man was given pure science. Science achieved its purpose to free man's mind from superstition but it came with a price. Besides the negative consequences of the industrial revolution and technology wars which nearly destroyed the planet, science was fostering selfishness and greed on an unimaginable scale worldwide and began to push the spiritual development of man, the very reason man is born onto this earth, to the sideline. In this quagmire of thousands of different denominations based more on an external belief system like ceremonies, sacred places, religious idols, etc. than common sense, technological developments endangering the survival of the planet as a whole and above all the proliferating mentality of greed, required God to enlighten mankind about the relationship between science and spirituality.

[11] A revelation which again explains the true origin of man, the purpose of man here on earth and the further spiritual development of man in the beyond. A revelation which also puts science into perspective and refocusses man's attention to its inner spiritual destination. To this extent another article has been published by the title "Intelligence, the Foundation of Matter" which is an elaboration of the micro cosmos (elementary particles) based on the teachings of the NR compared to the findings of modern science. The focus of this article is on the macro cosmos (universe) and beyond, providing a sensible, uncomplicated, complete picture of the origin of man and the physical as well as spiritual universe.

Structure of the universe

[12] Figure 2 is a simplified diagram of the structure of the universe as outlined by the New Revelation. It starts with millions of solar systems orbiting a central sun called a galaxy. Millions of galaxies orbiting another bigger central hub together forming a super-galaxy. Millions of super-galaxies in turn orbiting another massive centre constitute a super-super galaxy. And on the final level exactly seven million super-super galaxies are orbiting one colossal central universe sun. Thus the NR distinguishes between five different classes of suns. The planetary sun, the central galaxy sun, the central super-galaxy sun, the central super-super galaxy sun and the central universe sun. In the NR these suns (systems) are referred to as planetary suns (solar system), para central suns (galaxy), sun region (super-galaxy) and sun universe (super-super galaxy) while the total universe is called a shell globe. To simplify the appellation the more common terminology of 'galaxy' has been adopted.

[13] If the planet Pluto marks the outer border, then the diameter of our solar system is about 0.0013 light-years or 80 AU. The NR states that the star Sirius, the actual central sun of our galaxy, is orbited by 200 million suns (solar systems). Based on an average distance of 6.57 light years between solar systems of nearby stars, the diameter for the Sirius galaxy can be calculated at 105,000 light-years. Assuming that a super-galaxy contains 50 million orbiting galaxies and the average distance between galaxies is 9.9 million

light-years, its diameter can be estimated at 2 billion (2×10^9) light-years. Suppose a super-super galaxy has 25 million orbiting super-galaxies, its diameter can be approximated at 6.5 trillion (6.5×10^{12}) light-years. The volume of the central sun of a galaxy, super-galaxy or super-super galaxy always exceeds the combined volume of all the suns, planets, moons and comets in its gravitational realm by a million to a billion times. Considering the five classes of suns of which there is only one central universe sun, as well as the interlinked grouping of three galaxy classes (galaxies, super-galaxies and super-super galaxies), there are perhaps a lot more gravitational forces out there than fully appreciated by modern science which might in turn explain the phenomenon of dark matter and dark energy.

Fig. 2: Structure of the universe as portrayed by the New Revelation.

[14] Thus the NR states a structured universe in which all galaxies belong to either a super galaxy or a super-super galaxy. It goes further and describes a single central universe sun which is orbited by precisely 7 million super-super galaxies forming together a universe. But astronomy is not for the faint hearted and the central universe sun at the heart of the universe is given a diameter of 1.59×10^{36} light years and its name is the star Regulus in the constellation of Leo. Its distance from earth is given as 7.93×10^{47} light years and its volume is one million times the total volume of the many billions of all its orbiting galaxy suns, planetary suns, planets, moons and comets together. Interestingly in ancient cultures Regulus has many names as the Babylonian astronomers knew the star as Sharru ("the King"), the Persians called it Miyan ("the Centre") and in India the star was called Maghā ("the Mighty").

[15] According to modern science, however, Regulus, also known as Alpha Leonis, is the brightest star in the constellation Leo and the 21st brightest star in the night sky. It has an apparent magnitude of 1.35 and lies at a distance of only 79.3 light years from Earth. This does not in the slightest way corresponds with the distance given by the NR of 8×10^{47} light years. So where does the discrepancy come from? When looking closer, Regulus appears singular, but is actually a quadruple star system composed of four stars that are organized into two pairs of which one star has not yet been identified. My take is that only one of the four stars is the actual central sun but its distance and size measurement is obscured by the other much closer lying stars. Not meaning to upset anyone but the distance measurement methods might also not be that

accurate as it is depicted by official science. Besides, science has jumped from one galaxy during the mid 1800s to several billion galaxies today. Similar giant leaps may also occur in future as technology improves.

[16] In Hell to Heaven, volume 2, chapter 299, paragraph 8, the NR has the following to say about the central universe sun: *“Say I: “This is a major and central sun around which exactly seven million super-super galaxies orbit and move, but it is also exactly one million times larger than all of the seven million super-super galaxies together. Its diameter is two octillion earth miles. Light, with the greatest electro-magnetic speed, calculated as forty thousand earth miles per second, would take many thousand trillion earth years to get from one pole to the other on this sun!”* The term ‘super-super galaxy’ was introduced by the translator for better clarification instead of the direct old Austrian German translation of “Sonnen-Allalle” meaning ‘sun-all-all’ or ‘sun-universe-universes’. The comparison *“one million times larger than the seven million super-super galaxies”* refers to the net matter volume of the super-super galaxies thus excluding the inner space between galaxies, suns, planets, moons and comets. Octillion in this case equals the French, Canadian and German octillion, namely 10^{48} and not the British/US octillion which is equal to 10^{27} . ‘Earth miles’ refers here to one German mile which equals 7.5km. Hence, if forty-thousand is multiplied by 7.5km, it yields 300,000km/sec which is the speed of light.

[17] When asked about the distance between the central universe sun and earth, the Lord replied as follows: *“Say I: “One decillion miles are sufficient to compress it to the apparent diameter of Venus. Any further calculations I leave to your own delight!”* Again, decillion refers here to the French, Canadian and German decillion meaning 10^{60} , while the British/US decillion relates to 10^{33} . This remark implies that the distance between earth and the central universe sun is actually much further than one decillion German miles. Nevertheless, using the above particulars a few interesting calculations can be made. Given 9.46×10^{12} km in one light-year, the diameter of the central universe sun amounts to a staggering 1.59×10^{36} light-years with a volume of 2.09×10^{108} cubic light-years! Assuming that the earth lies halfway between the central universe sun and the outer edge of the universe, a diameter and volume for the universe can be calculated to be 3.17×10^{48} light-years and 1.67×10^{145} cubic light-years respectively. This would yield a matter to space ratio for the universe of 1.25×10^{-37} . All space is filled with a living ether as fully explained in the article “Intelligence, the foundation of matter”.

[18] Just to put the above figures into perspective, official science estimates the diameter of the universe at 93 billion or 93×10^9 light-years compared to the 3.17×10^{48} light-years of the NR. Rightly so some astronomers are speaking about a ‘visible universe’, acknowledging the possibility of a much bigger universe. An excellent summary article to support the case for incredible large super structures in space by modern astronomy has been published on vice.com by Becky Ferreira (November 2019). The opening paragraph of the article titled “There’s Growing Evidence That the Universe Is Connected by Giant Structures” reads as follows: *“Scientists are finding that galaxies can move with each other across huge distances, and against the predictions of basic cosmological models. The reason why it could change everything we think we know about the universe.”* Again, science begins to confirm the statements made by the NR already 150 years ago.

[19] Figure 3 is a schematic of a shell globe as described by the New Revelation. The universe is encapsulated by an impenetrable, many millions of light-years thick outer shell, hence the name shell globe. Unlike galaxies which are disk shaped, the shell globe is a sphere. Imaging oneself standing on the outer edge of such a shell globe, the next neighbouring shell globe would be visible as a hardly visible shimmering dot in distant space. Only the central universe sun and the central suns of the 7 million super-super galaxies are light producing by means of

Fig. 3: A Shell Globe according to the New Revelation.

burning gasses. All other super- galaxy-, galaxy- and solar system suns are only light reflectors as will be explained below. The inside of the impenetrable outer shell is also a perfect mirror, reflecting all the light produced by the central universe sun and the super-super galaxy suns back to the inside of the shell globe.

[20] Given a structured universe as described above, it can be assumed that 99% of all stars and galaxies visible to us on earth, even with the most advanced telescopes, form actually part of our very own super-super galaxy. Only some of the remaining seven million super-super galaxies would be visible, if so, as tiny little specks, despite having a diameter of 3.3×10^{12} light years. It would not be possible at all to look inside neighbouring super-super galaxies.

[21] There exist countless many shell globes in infinitive space. Everywhere there is the greatest order in God's creation. Be it the structure of atoms or the arrangement of shell globes. The shell globes are fixed in space and do not move relative to each other. There does not exist any life in the space between shell globes. All life is contained inside of all the shell globes. But more about this later on in this article.

[22] It is perhaps worth noting that it is stated in the NR that the super-super galaxy systems have some kind of a dual movement around the central universe sun. The first being the normal orbital movement around the central universe sun with the "*speed of thought*". The second movement is a kind of oscillating motion where at times the super-super galaxy suns are closer to the central universe sun and at times closer to the outer shell. This oscillating movement might have something to do with an expanding universe phenomenon as observed by mainstream science. It is further stated that when the super-super galaxy sun is close to the central universe sun it is charged with a positive psycho electromagnetic substance and when closer to the outer shell it is getting charged with a negative psycho electromagnetic substance. Only if sufficiently charged with both psycho electromagnetic substances will the super-super galaxy sun be able to develop super-galaxies, galaxies and solar systems. Now, there are many places in the NR where the reference 'speed of light' has been used. So, why mention the analogy to "speed of thought" when it comes to the orbital speed of super-super galaxy systems? The answer to this rather intriguing question can be found when using the orbital speed equation to calculate the orbital speed of the super-super galaxy sun. It takes a lot of courage to say this but it seems that we, implying our and all other super-super galaxies, are moving through space with many times over the speed of light!

[23] The enormous distances as mentioned above brings us to the age and origin of the universe or the shell globe. The Lord explains the age of the central universe sun as follows: "*If you assign a thousand times a thousand earth years to a tiniest grain of sand dust and fill the whole earth with it according to size, width and thickness, the oceans not excluded, then such calculated time period would still be way to short for such a sun.*" Allocating four grains of sand dust to one cubic millimetre then this would result in 4.33×10^{36} years. In the book Earth and Moon chapter 53 a more direct reference is given for the age of the central universe sun, namely, "several decillion years", implying more than 1×10^{60} years! Compare this to the age of the universe as suggested by mainstream science of only 13.5 billion or 13.5×10^9 years. It is further explained that the central suns of the countless shell globes gradually precipitated out of the ether to form an ever increasing denser gigantic large lump of mass. The ethereal dust cloud surrounding this lump settled to form the outer shell. Just like our sun, also the central universe sun rotates around its own axis. Once the structure of the shell globe was in place, non describable huge explosions occurred on the central universe sun to drive out super-super- and super galaxy suns which began to orbit the central universe sun while the super-galaxy suns began to orbit the super-super galaxy suns. Over unimaginable long periods of time subsequent galaxy- and solar system suns were ejected from the central- and super-super galaxy suns from which eventually planets evolved through asteroid/comet ejections growing into terrestrial bodies. Just like all forms of matter are born, grow and decay, so does shell globes, all super-super-, super-galaxies, galaxies and solar systems come into existence, grow and eventually die, a process which continues until this very day and is well known to modern day astronomers. This process is vital to the freeing of the bound conscious spiritual content in matter – the overall purpose of the physical creation.

[24] The above explanation of the origin of the universe differs markedly from the generally accepted singularity and big bang theory. The big bang theory suggests that all billions and billions of galaxies originated more or less at the same time namely shortly after the big bang about 13.5 billion years ago which, compared to the NR, is merely a blink of an eye. The age of our solar system is estimated by science to be 4.5 billion years old, a mere 3 times older than the entire universe. It also implies that our solar system would have orbited the Milky-Way centre only 36 times given an orbital time of 250 million years (1 galactic year), hardly sufficient for a newly ejected sun to settle into a circular orbit and develop its own planetary system which requires many million orbits to accomplish.

[25] Over the past 150 years science made progressive discoveries to gradually confirm the statements made in the NR between 1840 and 1865. The advancements of science regarding astronomy are summarized in Table 1. Contrary to the mainstream view of astronomers during the mid 1800s when it was generally believed that the Milky Way was the only galaxy in space, the NR gives a clear description of many billions of galaxies to exist in our universe. Only in 1925, 60 years after the death of Lorber, did Edwin Hubble discover, with the then newly constructed 2.57 m telescope on Mount Wilson, that the nebula in M31, M33 and NGC 6822 turned out to be galaxies, breaking all barriers with regard to the then current view of the universe. But the NR went further than this and states that many millions of galaxies form an interdependent gravity group called a super-galaxy and held together by a gigantic large central sun. These enormous structures can be compared to the so called *galaxy clusters* of mainstream science as discovered during the 1960's with the newly constructed radio telescopes. The arrangement of super-galaxies orbiting a central sun to form super-super galaxies of the NR relate to *super clusters* of modern astronomy as published during the 1980s. It must be emphasized that in none of the galaxy structures, clusters and super clusters included, a central sun has been discovered so far. Even the Milky Way is said to have a nucleus consisting of large suns and black holes. But a single central gigantic sun at the very centre of the Milky Way has not been discovered. The intense light at the centre of galaxies makes it quite difficult to study the nucleus. In time, however, astronomers might obtain more information about the so called quasars occurring at the centre of galaxies.

Table 1: Comparison between statements made by the NR before 1865 and the findings by mainstream science.

New Revelation (before 1865)	Mainstream science
Planetary system	Solar system
Billions of galaxies with central galaxy suns	Multiple galaxies confirmed by Hubble in 1925
Millions of super-galaxies with central suns	Satellite galaxies, clusters* of galaxies and quasars – 1960s ?
Millions of super-super galaxies with central suns	Super Clusters* of galaxies – 1980s ?
Shell globe with central universe sun	Not confirmed
Multiple universes (shell globes)	speculated
	*galaxy clusters bound together by gravity it has also been observed that satellite galaxies are orbiting larger galaxies

Formation of solar systems

[26] As stated already, all suns are bodies ejected by either the central universe sun or the super-super galaxy suns. These suns are then caught by the gravitational field of any of the existing super-galaxy- or galaxy suns. Once in orbit around the centre of a galaxy, the new solar system sun drives out asteroids and comets of all sizes. As these asteroids/comets race through space they are growing in size by “feeding” on the ether and by amalgamation with other asteroids (Ultima Thule/Arrokoth serves as a striking example of this). Over many millions of years these initially very eccentric orbits become more and more centralized ellipses/circles and the grown asteroids/comets will eventually develop into new planets on the fringe of the solar system (e.g. Pluto, Haumea, Eris, etc.) (Fig. 4). Still growing in size they will develop an atmosphere, initially a rather very thick atmosphere (Jupiter, Saturn, Uranus and Neptune). Once reaching a critical mass and volume the newly formed planets will begin their long journey back to the sun again. Thus Mercury will be the next planet to fall

Fig. 4: Formation of planets according to the NR.

back into the sun. During their journey back to the sun, the planets are losing mass. Note the recent discovery of the considerable shrivelling in size of Mercury. The reason for this is that planets are giving up freed spiritual content during their lifetime, resulting in a loss of mass.

[27] This planet forming process differs markedly from the generally accepted model for the formation of a solar system as suggested by mainstream science which is based on the collapse of a nebula forming a disk of dust which gradually develops into a proto-sun at the centre surrounded by proto-planets.

[28] Continuing this development of the planets as described by the NR, it is noticeable that the four planets nearest to the sun are rather small in size and have only a very thin atmosphere compared to the so called gas-giants which have a very thick atmosphere. It is now not that difficult to infer that Jupiter is the next planet in line to lose its thick atmosphere and become an ordinary much, much smaller "rock-planet". The rings of Jupiter and Saturn can be considered remnants of this atmosphere-losing process (Fig. 5). The reason for the relatively thick atmosphere of the outer planets is to catch more sunlight in order to provide more heat to the rocky core. But a planet like Jupiter or Saturn could not exist at the position of for instance Venus and retain its thick atmosphere. The intensity of light from the sun would generate too much heat for the atmosphere to sustain.

Fig. 5: Planets of the solar system (NASA website).

[29] In passing, according to the NR the asteroid belt between Mars and Jupiter, is a former planet which has exploded to form the ring of debris. The NR also states that the planet earth and the original asteroid belt planet, form an exception and did not originate from our sun but instead were directly ejected by the central universe sun and were caught by the gravity of our sun. Also modern science concluded that the temperature of our sun would not have been sufficient to have produced the wide variety of heavy minerals present on earth and that the planet earth must have originated from another much larger sun. Because of the earth's origin it can be expected that the variety of minerals of other planets in our solar system will be a lot less than those found on earth.

The sun

[30] Perhaps the most controversial revelation by the NR is that fusion as we know it, does not form the source of energy on the sun. The NR describes the sun as being enveloped by an atmosphere with a super smooth outer mirror surface. This mirror surface has the ability to reflect light from all surrounding stars which forms the main source of light on the sun. A secondary source of light on the sun is created through the sun's rotation around its own axis whereby the surface of the outer atmosphere generates friction with the

surrounding ether. Thus the sun as a perfect mirror provides reflected light, friction light and heat to its orbiting planets. It is also stated that the heat is generated at the target and not at the source as is the case with any mirror. This implies that the sun might not be as hot as it is generally believed. While space is filled with light everywhere, the temperature of space is always 2.73 Kelvin (-270.42 Celsius, -454.75 Fahrenheit) according to official science. But when placing an object anywhere in space, the temperature on the surface of this object immediately starts to rise.

Fig. 6: The structure of the sun according to the New Revelation.

[31] In the article "Intelligence, the Foundation of Matter", the concept of the ether has been discussed in great detail. Sufficient to say here that contrary to Einstein, an ether with particle movement in fact does exist, and some modern scientists dare to rediscover the ether which was a taboo subject for far too long (Prof. Robert B. Laughlin, Stanford). How to align a moving ether with a questionable relativity is a discussion for another day. Because official science is not allowed to accept a "moving" particle ether, conveniently the term *solar wind* has been invented. When a comet approaches the sun it gathers gravitational speed and starts to develop a visible tail. The tail is the result of the dust/vapour cloud surrounding the comet colliding with an increasing denser ether near the sun. This denser ether is called by official science solar wind in order to avoid the banned term 'ether'. So far it eludes me to find a satisfactory answer to why the bending of light during the eclipse experiment of Eddington in 1919 to confirm Einstein's relativity, could not have been ascribed to a denser ether near the sun.

[32] The spiral shape of galaxies might support the idea of a return journey of solar suns to the centre. The many so called "black holes" discovered at the centre of galaxies are in fact remnants of dying suns as it is also confirmed by mainstream science. In line with the above description of suns encapsulated by a mirror smooth atmosphere, producing the actual light, it can be inferred that if a sun gets too close to the galaxy centre, it loses its atmosphere (just like planets) and subsequently loses its ability to produce light which in turn makes the sun appear as a black hole. A dying sun which has lost its light generating atmosphere, still exerts a powerful gravitational force on its environment. Naturally, if a sun dies, irrespective the class, all its surrounding galaxies, solar systems and planets will also cease to exist. With regard to black holes, your attention is drawn to the findings of scientist Laura Mersini-Houghton of the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, who has proven mathematically that black holes (as propagated by mainstream science) can never come into being as it is impossible for stars to collapse and form a singularity.

[33] The diameter of the sun is given by the NR as 1.5 million km which compares favourably to the 1.39 million km of modern astronomy. Just like all the planets also the sun has an outer atmosphere and an inner solid core. It is further stated that the inner solid core of the sun consists of six spheres hovering inside of each other with a seventh most inner solid core (as schematically indicated in Fig. 6). This kind of pattern can be found in all bodies of the universe but in an underdeveloped pattern in planets and even less so in moons and asteroids. In our sun the space between the spheres ranges from 7,500 km tot 22,500 km while the outer most atmosphere is about 37,500 km thick. Making a few assumptions as to the thickness of the spheres, a diameter of 975,000 km can be calculated for the innermost solid core.

[34] Deviating substantially from mainstream science, it is said in the NR that our solar system is orbiting the star Sirius in 28,000 years. It is further stated that Sirius is orbited by 200 million solar system suns. This implies that Sirius is the centre of a so called dwarf galaxy which in turn is orbiting the Milky Way centre. In the language of the NR this makes the Milky Way a super-galaxy which leads to the conclusion that the Milky Way is in fact a constellation of millions of ordinary galaxies. According to the research by Dr William Brown, Colorado State University, as outlined in his article "A Sirius Revolution", the ancient Egyptian and Mayan astronomers were well aware of the fact that our solar system is orbiting Sirius. But he takes this a step further and explains that the Sirius system is in fact orbiting another centre called Alcyone which in turn is orbiting the Milky Way centre. If this is correct the Milky Way then is in fact a super-super galaxy, with Alcyone being a super-galaxy and the Sirius system forming an ordinary galaxy. As referenced in Wikipedia,

Alcyone is a multiple star system in the constellation of Taurus, approximately 440 light years from the Sun and is part of the Pleiades cluster, one of the nearest open clusters to earth.

The Universe

[35] Concerning the dimensions of the universe it can be said that already twice major corrections by science had to be made. The first after Hubble's discovery of distant galaxies and the second after the discovery of quasars during the late 1950s. Both corrections brought official science closer to the statements made by the NR during the mid 1800s.

[36] As promised above let's turn our attention again to the arrangement of shell globes in space. In the NR the Lord teaches us that the nearly infinite number of shell-globes in space have the outer shape of a man (Fig. 7). This should not come as a too great surprise to us since also our own bodies are made up of atoms, electrons and molecules in a similar fashion. And as explained in the article "Intelligence, the Foundation of Matter", also our intangible, indestructible souls consists of a nearly infinitive number of intelligence particles called *specifica*. Therefore all humans everywhere inside the infinitive number of shell globes, perhaps differing in size and irrespective if material or spiritual, but they all have the same human shape. In God's order it cannot be otherwise. This inconceivable large figure can be called the *cosmic man* also known as Lucifer ('carrier of light'). Being captured in matter he is in bondage and deprived of all power, not capable of moving even his eyelids. From all the endless number of shell globes comprising his being, his consciousness (spirit) is incarcerated in the centre of planet earth. This cosmic man is driven by the will of God with inconceivable speed through the ether in an indescribable large circle whereby he receives his nourishment.

[37] The cosmic man, however, did not just happen to form out of thin air. To better understand God's creation, you are referred to another article by the same author titled "Understanding Genesis". Since eternity infinity was filled with divine intelligence and divine power also referred to as the eternal fire of God. But at some point, love, the most inner essence of God, prompted Him to replicate Himself and create beings out of Himself and gradually given the same wisdom, power and free willingness as God Himself. The purpose was to create beings who would recognize and love their Creator out of their own free will. It is this very same love prompting us to procreate children today. Creating beings to His own image was the easy part. Giving them free willingness would even prove for God a challenge and would take many eternities to achieve. During the six days or better said, six epochs of creation, God educated spiritual man to become free thinking and free willing beings, capable of creating what God Himself could create. But when God created man He also created a framework for His creation to develop and ripen, called God's order.

[38] Out of the eternal fire, God created a second layer of intelligence which can be referred to as the thoughts and ideas of God. Within this layer the thoughts and ideas of God were attributed a form and served as a foundation for the creation, development and ripening of free willing spiritual beings. Establishing this second layer was necessary to create some space between the perfect divine fire and the newly created beings to develop their own free willingness based on their own recognitions, experiences and actions, independent from God's almighty eternal fire. At the same time God also created a framework or better stated a constitution called God's order for the newly created beings to adhere to. Already at that stage did God implant a spark of the perfect divine fire, the divine spirit, inside each newly created being to provide it with self-consciousness, life and power but also to be able to eventually achieve God's likeness. In the beginning the divine spirit had to be isolated within the created beings to allow them to develop their own free willingness free from the influence of God's almightiness. For the beings to become really free, God had to endow man with the ability to choose between right and wrong but also the urge to transgress God's order. So it took God many aeons to teach man God's order, to educate man about the consequences of his choices and to allow man to experience these consequences. This initial educational process, taking many aeons to accomplish, was divided by Moses into the six days or epochs of creation in Genesis 1.

[39] From the very beginning God realized that if He created truly free willing beings, that some of the creatures might start to reject their own Creator and that He, as their God, could not do anything about it, if

Fig. 7: The Cosmic Man.

He did not want to interfere with His almightiness to curb their free willingness and turn them into string guided puppets which effectively would mean destroying His own creation. This of course was impossible to happen. So when the first created, the most powerful of all the beings with the highest destination, became selfish, narcissistic and haughty despite being lovingly admonished over aeons, his soul, gradually distancing himself from the divine centre, started to become more and more dense to finally turn into matter. Effectively imprison himself into matter which he was told that it will happen and by doing so would lose all his glory and power and endure endless suffering. Still, he and his countless followers, decided to exercise their free will which, according to God's order, led to the creation of the cosmic man. The greatest pain was the loss of his previous unlimited freedom and enduring the physical 'must-laws' of matter. So the educational process of God still continues to this very day and will continue for many aeons to come until the last being is freed from matter and all matter has been dissolved. The creation of the cosmic man is also symbolised with the parable of the potter (Jeremiah 18,1-4) and his return journey is revealed to us by the prodigal son. Thus, day seven of the creation is still in progress.

[40] All people who ever lived and will be living in the future, including each one of us, is represented in the prodigal son, eventually destined to become endless times larger and infinitely more powerful than the fallen first born. To achieve this we just have to adhere to the principal of loving God above all and our fellow-man as ourselves with the utmost of humility.

[41] With the three articles "Structure of the Universe", "Intelligence, the Foundation of Matter" and "Understanding Genesis", it was aimed to provide a complete picture of the creation and its destiny as it was explained by the Creator Himself in the New Revelation. The reason for placing way too much emphasis on the physical side of the creation in this article was done in order to compare the facts provided in the NR with mainstream science. Thus going beyond this rather superficial summary and to explore the living spiritual depth of these deepest secrets of creation, you are encouraged to read the NR with an open and humble heart.